

Spectrophotometric determination of lisinopril in pharmaceutical formulations

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A new spectrophotometric method has been developed for the estimation of lisinopril (LSP) in pharmaceutical formulation. The method is based on the formation of a violet color with 0.3% (w/v) of ninhydrin solution in acetone, exhibiting absorption maximum at 410 nm. The violet colored chromogen formed is stable and Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range 10–40 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The method has been found to be applicable for quantitative estimation of LSP.

Lisinopril^{1,2}, an angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitor, is chemically 1-[N-(S)-1-carboxy-3-phenylpropyl]-L-lysyl-L-proline dihydrate. It is mainly used in treatment of hypertension³. The drug is also used as an adjunct in the treatment of congestive heart failure. USP² describes a HPLC method for the estimation of lisinopril (LSP) where acetonitrile in phosphate buffer is used as mobile phase. Other reported analytical methods are fluorimetric⁴, immuno assay⁵, GLC⁶ and HPLC⁷. In the present study, a simple, specific and convenient method is described to estimate LSP in tablet formulations.

Results and Discussion

The colored solution produced by mixing LSP and ninhydrin exhibited maximum absorption at 410 nm. The color was stable for more than 5 h. The optimum concentration for the estimation of LSP was established by varying one parameter at a time and keeping the other fixed and observing the effect of product on the absorbance of the colored species and incorporated in the procedure. Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range 10–40 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ (slope = 0.0032, $r = 1.000$, molar absorptivity = $1.854 \times 10^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The percentage recovery value (99.55%) indicates that there is no interference of the excipients present in the formulation. The standard deviation and coefficient of variation values obtained from five repeated experiments of each of the samples (Table 1) infer that the method may be used for precise estimation of LSP in routine analysis.

Experimental

An Elico SL 159 UV-VIS spectrophotometer was used. A 0.3% (w/v) solution of ninhydrin in acetone was used. A stock solution (1 mg ml^{-1}) of LSP was prepared in distilled

water.

Procedure : Tablet powder (equivalent to 10 mg of LSP) was dissolved and made upto 10 ml with distilled water, shaken well and filtered. To 0.4 ml of the filtrate representing 40 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, was added freshly prepared ninhydrin reagent (0.3% w/v; 1.5 ml). The contents were warmed on a water-bath for 10 min, then cooled to room temperature and the volume made upto 10 ml with distilled water. Its absorbance was measured at 410 nm against reagent blank. The absorbance for 40 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration of pure LSP was also measured at 410 nm for the calculation of drug content in tablets. The samples were also analysed by the HPLC method². The amount was calculated from the calibration graph.

Table 1. Analysis of lisinopril tablets*

Tablet	Amount found by		Percentage recovery ^b	Stand. dev.	Coeff. of variation
	Proposed method ^d	Reported method			
Sample 1	4.959	5.002	99.48	0.0050	0.1129
Sample 2	4.969	5.018	99.45	0.0061	0.1240
Sample 3	5.009	5.021	99.73	0.0091	0.1845

*Label claim = 5 mg. ^dEach result is the mean of five replicates.

^bRecovery of 0 mg, and 1 mg was added to pharmaceutical preparations.

To evaluate the accuracy, reproducibility and to check the interference of excipients in tablets, recovery study was performed. The recovery of the added standard was studied at three different levels, repeating each level five times. From the amount of drug found, the percentage recovery was calculated.

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References

1. "The Merck Index", 11th. ed., Merck & Co., Rahway, 1999, p. 869.
2. "The United States Pharmacopoeia, XXXIII", United States Pharmacopoeial Convention, Easton, 1995, p. 895.
3. "The Extra Pharmacopoeia", 30th. ed., eds. J. E. E. Reynolds, K. Parfitt and Matrindale, The Pharmaceutical Press, London, 1989, p. 487.
4. G. Iskender and B. Yarenci, *Acta Pharm. Tur.*, 1996, **38**, 65; K. Shepney, M. L. Rock. H. Patrica and P. Mojaverian, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 1998, **6**, 241.
5. P. J. Worland and B. Jarrott, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1976, **75**, 512.
6. A. B. Avandhanalu and A. R. R. Pantulu, *Indian Drugs*, 1994, **30**, 646.
7. W. Yiu-Chung and L. J. B. Gardon, *J. Chromatogr. B*, 1995, **673**, 306; R. T. Sane. G. R. Valiyare, V. M. Deshmukh. S. R. Singh and R. Sodhi, *Indian Drugs*, 1992, **29**, 558.